

MUSIC EDUCATION IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract. *This article describes the goals and tasks of music education and training in preschool educational institutions, and the formation of musical taste of school-aged children.*

Key words: *preschool education, music education, musical taste, training, education.*

The formation of musical taste of children of preschool age involves conscious perception of music. All musical-educational activities carried out in MTMs are aimed at forming noble qualities in children from the kindergarten age. The educational activities carried out in kindergartens serve the young generation to grow up as spiritually mature and well-rounded people. In the process of music lessons, children perceive the reality of life through musical images. Musical works suitable for their age leave an unforgettable impression on the students and enrich their spiritual world. If children's skills such as abstract thinking and logical memory grow in concrete activities such as work, math, and the world around us, in music classes, their figurative thinking, speech culture, musical learning, and the ability to feel beauty ability develops. Every musical activity conducted using special techniques awakens the pleasure of artistic sophistication in children and increases their interest in music.

Scientific methodical improvement of music training in every way, in accordance with the requirements of the times, is one of the urgent tasks facing future music leaders today. It is believed that these tasks can be carried out with the effective use of this educational guide, which contains methodical recommendations for conducting music lessons, examples of lesson plans, scenarios of mornings, holidays, and events held in kindergartens. we cry

The main goal of music education and upbringing in preschool educational institutions is to form the worldview of children from the kindergarten age, to develop musical taste, and in the process of teaching music to children, life is reflected in it. It should be noted that in order to realize the pedagogical goals and tasks set before music lessons, first of all, it is necessary to regularly develop children's musical skills and abilities. Children's musical learning and abilities consist of the following activities: - musical learning (the ability to feel the high and low pitch of musical sounds); – timbre reading (distinguishing musical sounds from each other); - a sense of

rhythm (moving to the music, keeping the music in memory, feeling and expressing it by stepping and clapping).

Children's musical abilities develop regularly during the implementation of all elements of musical training. The main tasks of music education in kindergartens are as follows: - to develop children's interest in music; - to enrich children's ideas about music by creating emotional feelings in the process of introducing them to musical works; - to develop children's creative abilities with the help of listening to music, singing, performing rhythmic movements to music, accompanying children's musical instruments; - nurturing children's voices, teaching and accustoming them to sing songs simply, fluently, freely, naturally and expressively; - to enjoy musical works, to develop musical taste and artistic thinking on this basis; - teaching to express the artistic images of the musical work in the form of games and dances during music lessons; - introducing children to our national values in music classes, teaching them to perform national musical and rhythmic movements accompanied by national musical instruments; - connecting the content of music classes with kindergarten life, participating in kindergarten events with learned tunes and songs. Organization of special mornings and concerts.

During music lessons, the child perceives life and surroundings through musical images. In the kindergarten, musical education is carried out in an integral connection with fiction and visual arts. Each music lesson conducted using special methods arouses artistic and aesthetic pleasure in children, shapes their feelings, develops creative thinking and speech. In addition, musical games and dances help children develop a sense of rhythm, agility and mobility skills, and help them grow properly. It is important for the child's mental and physical development. All musical educational and educational activities carried out in pre-school educational institutions are considered to be a component of education of refinement in the formation of noble qualities in the young generation from the kindergarten age.

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